

Teaching And Learning Before, During And The Current Period Of COVID-19 Pandemic: How The Academic Performance Of Students Are Impacted?

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: November 13, 2022</p> <p>Accepted: February 15, 2023</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : CAMSJ, COVID-19, Mode of teaching, Success rate</p> <hr/> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7641579</p>	<p><i>The pandemic caused by the Coronavirus has stricken hard every industry in the world. This includes the academic sector; everyone associated with the educational boards acknowledges that during the pandemic, teaching and learning methods must be altered due to conditions that have necessitated a forced adaptation of the learning approach. This paper investigates and assesses the impact of this transition on the academic performance of the students in the College of Applied Medical Sciences (CAMSJ) Jubail, Imam Abdul Rehman Bin Faisal University, Dammam, in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. To achieve this objective, the result sheets of students in the period before, during, and current COVID-19 pandemic were collected. Simple descriptive and inferential statistics were used to summarize the results and to test the significance of alternative teaching modalities. The findings of this study show that when teaching and learning techniques are adjusted, students' performance improves statistically significantly.</i></p>

Introduction

At the end of 2019, Wuhan, China, registered the first Coronavirus case (COVID-19) which has exponentially spread and resulted in a pandemic all over the world. On 11th March, 2020, the World Health Organization considered it a global pandemic (Organization WH., 2020) which caused an extreme change in the educational organizations and led to a sudden stoppage of most schools and universities and shift to distance learning all over the world (Mahdy et al., 2022). This was an obligatory challenge to modulate teaching approaches and assessment methods for online learning (virtual classes) for all the educational boards assuming the sudden shift will negatively influence the academic achievement of the students (Gin et al., 2021; Kimble-Hill et al., 2020). Students and teachers all over the world faced some challenges due to the swift transition to the online learning mode (Nazeefa et al., 2021, Parkes & Barrs 2021).

The Saudi Ministry of Education declared online classes to conduct the teaching-learning process, in a safe and secure environment. Within a few days, all universities including medical colleges were switched to online teaching (Tanveer et al., 2020) and continued this mode for three academic semesters. There are two ways to teach online: Synchronous classes that use live classes at the exact time using virtual sessions (Microsoft Teams, Zoom, etc.) and asynchronous classes that record lectures encompass significant delays in time between instruction and student (Fabrizz et al., 2021). Asynchronous technology was challenging for students because of the limited non-verbal communication while synchronous technology provides greater real-time interaction between students and teachers, and instant feedback that makes online learning more dynamic (Mohammed et al., 2020). Nowadays the conventional system is following hybrid learning, mixing both face-to-face and online learning ways. In particular, the health track was moved to a new educational learning system that can provide students with an appropriate online learning experience, to perform the various activities such as conducting lectures, providing teaching materials-assignments, and acquiring specific abilities and support skills (Ahmed et al., 2020).

Previous research studies have investigated students' perception and satisfaction towards online learning (e-Learning) and face-to-face learning, pre and during the pandemic. Some researchers found that remote learning is perceived as deficient in societal contacts, attendance, and synchronized efficient communication, on the other hand, it affords sundry benefits including suitability and time flexibility, a relaxed understanding of crucial perceptions and topics, and provides chances to work while learning (Bali & Liu, 2018; Cuthrell & Lyon, 2007). Other research discovered that although the levels of academic performance are similar to face-to-face and web-assisted activities, undergraduate students wanted to do face-to-face ones (Kemp & Grieve, 2014). Other studies agreed with social activities and classroom dynamics which are crucial for face-to-face learning methods to inspire learning engagement that results in effective, fruitful, and successful learning with improved results (Hurst et al., 2013; Sharma & Alvi, 2021).

Undeniably, before COVID-19 pandemic physical attending classrooms have the advantage of delivering immediate feedback about the impact of the teaching process for both instructors and students. In the conventional classroom, teachers can monitor students' body language, behavior, and these non-verbal cues aid teachers to adjust their teaching instantly to consider the best suitable requirements of the students (Khalil et al., 2020).

Nambiar, 2020, noted that dissatisfaction with online learning leads to face-to-face learning, achieving more positive accuracy than online learning in social, interaction, satisfaction, and overall excellence. In addition to technical support, it plays an essential factor in determining the satisfaction of an online course. Even if online lessons are described as appropriate in terms of effective time management. Both beneficiaries reported online structuring and inefficiency compared to classroom mode.

Some researchers compared differences in perceptions of similar students in higher education before and during COVID-19 pandemic. One of these studies confirmed that students prefer a hybrid (mixed) mode of learning (Sharma & Alvi, 2021). Other enumerates the positive aspect of online learning majority confirmed that it could be done from the comfort of the home which saves time to travel and commute, flexibility to attend the classes without rushing to reach college. Other positive things reported were their ability to record the classes helped in referring to them later. Less interference from classmates and anxiety when asking questions (Nambiar, 2020).

According to Supriya et al., 2021, the transition to online learning did not negatively affect students' performance, however, the negative impacts of students on this transition were reflected in students' surveys, especially on students' awareness of course content and interactions teachers. It seems that these perceptions don't have a stronger impact on their academic achievements (Supriya et al., 2021). Other studies have shown that students recognize the benefits of teacher flexibility and the way of assessment. This was reported by other research studies which show that students were not satisfied with learning after away from distance lessons (Petlion & McNeil, 2020). In other studies, students' experience agrees with the lack of interaction, professional preparation, and university communities (Means & Neisler, 2021).

The current study is a longitudinal follow-up in fall 2019 to Spring 2022 (before, during, and the current period of the COVID-19 pandemic) to determine the effect of different teaching-learning approaches (face-to-face, online and hybrid mode) on student's performance at (CAMSJ, IAU-Kingdom of Saudi Arabia).

Method

Data description and collection procedure

The study sample consisted of the courses taken by the students enrolled in different 4-year Bachelor of Science programs at the College of Applied Medical Sciences in Jubail (CAMSJ), Imam Abdulrahman bin Faisal University (IAU), Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA). To overcome the heterogeneity issues and to test the significance of the success rates among the courses of different programs, we limit our study to the same students who remained at the college during all three modes of teaching. These students attended face-to-face classes before the pandemic, online classes during the pandemic, and shifted to hybrid classes corresponding to the current period in 2021-2022. Number of students enrolled during the study period in different courses was from 24 to 48. They were enrolled in one of the three programs: Bachelor of Science in Anesthesia Technology, Bachelor of Science in Respiratory Care, and Bachelor of Science in Neuroscience Technology. During their study period, students had to take some common courses including microbiology, anatomy, physiology, biostatistics, research methodology, and medical ethics. On the other hand, specialized approved courses were also taken by the students in their respective programs (Figure 1)

Hybrid	Ethics in Respiratory Care (33)	Clinical Anesthesia IV (40)	Clinical Practice III (43)
	Pulmonary Rehabilitation (33)	Management in Healthcare Professions (37)	Long Term Monitoring (42)
	Advanced Pulmonary Function Testing (33)	Recovery and Anesthetic Related Complications (40)	Intraoperative Monitoring I (43)
	Neonatal and Pediatric Respiratory Care (33)	Anesthetic Management for Surgeries and Procedures III (40)	Nerve Conduction and Electromyogram II (43)
	Clinical Practice IV (33)	Total Quality Management (34)	Evoked Potential II (43)
	Research Methodology (33)	Research Methodology (40)	Research Methods and Applied Statistics (44)
Online			Medical Ethics (42)
	Biostatistics (27)		Introduction to Research Methods (42)
	Basic Pulmonary Function		Nerve Conduction and

	Testing (32)		Electromyogram I (43)
	Clinical Practice III (33)		Neuromuscular Disorders (43)
	Health Information Systems (24)		Evoked Potentials I (43)
	Management of Mechanical Ventilation (32)		Clinical practice II (43)
	Respiratory Diseases II (30)	Biostatistics (40)	Electroencephalogram II (42)
	Clinical Practice II (34)	Ethical and Medico Legal Aspects in Anesthesia (36)	Clinical practice I (42)
	Respiratory Diseases I (28)	Anesthesia for Patients with Coexisting Diseases (34)	Behavioral sciences (44)
	Respiratory Pharmacology (27)	Regional Anesthesia and Pain Management (40)	Imaging and Sonography (43)
	Introduction to Mechanical Ventilation (33)	Anesthetic Management for Surgeries and Procedures II (38)	Electroencephalogram I (42)
	Blood Gases (33)	Clinical Anesthesia III (34)	Central Nervous System Disorders (43)
Face to face	Economic system in Islam (26)		Physiology (44)
	Physiology (28)	Physiology (43)	Anatomy (44)
	Anatomy (39)	Anatomy (48)	Microbiology (45)
	Microbiology (36)	Microbiology (44)	Economic system in Islam (44)
	Introduction to RC profession (28)	Economic system in Islam (42)	Introduction to Clinical Neurophysiology Profession (44)
	Medical Gas Therapy (33)	Introduction to Anesthesia Technology Profession (46)	Electronics and Instrumentations for Electro Neurophysiology (44)
	Biochemistry (28)	General Pharmacology (44)	
	Bachelor in respiratory care	Bachelor in Anesthesia Technology	Bachelor in Neuroscience Technology

Note: Numbers in parenthesis represent number of students enrolled in respective course

Figure 1 Course scheme in different programs over different modes of teaching

The success rate of each course in all the academic years for all the programs served as a key comparison factor for assessing the performance variances between online, face-to-face, and hybrid modes of teaching. Of the total 66 courses in 4-year period of Bachelor of Sciences in all the programs, 19 (29%) were taken face-to-face, 29 (44%) were taken online, and 18 (27%) were taken as hybrid mode of teaching. The composition of the study set was based on government-enforced COVID-19 regulations and occasional pandemic fluctuations.

Before pandemic, the face-to-face classes were held once a week in the college classrooms. Each class lasted 1 hour and 50 minutes. It involved lectures delivery, discussions, Q/A sessions and feedbacks. During pandemic, the lecture lasted the same duration and covered the same content as the face-to-face course but was offered entirely online using the Blackboard learning system, with the help of Microsoft teams and Zoom classes. The faculty combined lecture slides, classroom discussions, textbook learning, assignments, collaborative projects and assessment to get students involved in the online learning process. The online lectures were also recorded to be available to the students in future. Lastly, in the hybrid teaching, a blended mode of face-to-face and online classes were adopted. The three teaching modalities have same assessment methods (written midterm and final exam (MCQ + essay), laboratory exam (written +practical), quizzes and assignment). The attendance rate is registered but is not included in the final grade. The written exams are considered as the important percent of the final grade which is more than 75% for all courses. The MCQ part of the exam is corrected using OMR sheet scanner and the essay part by two faculty members to check effectively on the reliability and validity of the assigned mark value.

All courses were taught by the full-time faculty at IAU. The faculty was comprised of professors and lecturers with extensive experience in both classroom teaching and online teaching. The faculty was also assisted by the

demonstrators during the course and laboratory work. They were considered excellent instructors with great communication and management skills.

Test equipment: In this study, student grades were put into operation based on course pass rates and final grades. Final course grades are derived from different tests, assignments, mid-term, and final exam results. The above four reviews were valid and relevant. They helped assess students' abilities and provide objective measures of

achievement. Final grades have also been converted from numerical grades to traditional GPA letters.

The success rates of each course and the students' course grades were obtained from the CAMSJ office of Vice dean of Academic affairs (VDAA). The VDAA issued the files to the team of researchers after approval to maintain confidentiality.

Statistical analysis

To answer our research questions, we have used naïve descriptive as well as inferential statistics techniques. To know the summary statistics of the success rates, we have used simple descriptive measures. Similarly, we have used ANOVA to test the significance between alternative teaching modalities. To investigate the student's grades, we have used contingency table and chi-square test. The data were analyzed using Stata 16.0 version and charts were made using MS Excel. These estimated values were subsequently used to draw conclusions and validate the hypothesis.

Results and Discussion

In our first research inquiry, we looked at whether there was a considerable variation in success rates of same students between face-to-face (level 3 in 2019-2020), online (level 5+6 in 2020-2021) and hybrid learning (level 7 in 2021-2022). Level 4 in 2019-2020 was skipped from analysis because only exams have been taken online. We analyzed the data using traditional descriptive and inferential statistical techniques. These analyses can determine (i) fluctuations in success rates, (ii) annual trends in success rates and (iii) statistically significant relationships between teaching modes and success rates, making this type of comparison especially useful to determine a sample set that can be expanded to a larger population.

Table 1 shows summary statistics for overall and annual success rates. Visually expressing the difference between results and differences is a general breakdown of success rates. The average success rate for each year is similar, with face-to-face scoring at 95.7%, online scoring at 99.4% and a hybrid scoring at 99.8%. The SDs in all the groups were quite different. Student success rates for face-to-face show a greater difference compared to success rates achieved in other years. An upward trend in the success rates reveals that the intervention of digital learning mechanism in teaching-learning environment had improved academic performance of medical students in the CAMSJ.

Table 1 Summary statistics of success rate

Academic years	Mean	SD	Min.	Max.
2019-2020 (Face-to-Face)	0.957	0.080	0.72	1.00
2020-2021 (Online)	0.994	0.015	0.95	1.00
2021-2022 (Hybrid)	0.998	0.005	0.98	1.00
Overall	0.984	0.047	0.72	1.00

Figure 1 shows the scheme of study in different programs over different modes of teaching. Number of students enrolled in each course has been shown in the parenthesis. The era of face-to-face teaching was before COVID-19 when the students started their bachelors' programs. The courses taken during face-to-face teaching were of freshmen levels. During the COVID-19, students were shifted exclusively to online teaching mode where they studied sophomore and junior level courses. Finally, when restrictions of COVID-19 were partly relaxed, students were shifted to hybrid mode of study where they studied senior level courses.

Our second research inquiry was to assess if there has been a distinction in letter grades among face-to-face, online and hybrid learners. Do students overall performance range with respect to letter grades? Figure 2 shows the percentage change in grades during three academic years.

Figure 2 Percent change in grades over the teaching modes

To know the statistical significance for different teaching modes, we run the ANOVA* test with the hypothesis that the average success rate for all three years and alternative teaching modes are the same.

Table 2 shows the results of ANOVA. The p-value is 0.0080 which shows that average success rates are statistically significant. The effect size was calculated at 0.1115. To answer the second research question, we performed the post-hoc analysis testing Benferroni's least significance difference (LSD) formula. It also shows highly significant results between the face-to-face versus online, and face-to-face versus hybrid modes of teaching. Contrary to this, no significantly different affect was found between online versus hybrid modes of teaching.

Table 2 ANOVA results

Source		SS	df	MS	F		Prob > F
Between Groups		0.020	2	0.010	5.22		0.0080
Within Groups		0.123	63	0.0019			
Total		0.1434	65	0.0022			
Bonferroni's LSD test		Face-to-face vs Online		Face-to-face vs Hybrid		Online vs Hybrid	
	Statistic	0.037		0.041		0.0037	
	P-value	0.008		0.012		1.000	

We observe the better students' performance during online and hybrid classes. Alternatively, there is an increasing trend observed for students' grades A and B during online classes. Similarly, an increasing trend was observed for hybrid classes, as well. It shows that students improved their marks more swiftly during online and hybrid classes as compared to face-to-face classes.

Table 3 displays grades distribution by course delivery mode and indicates the performance measures of students in face-to-face, online, and hybrid learning by grades classification. The variation in students' performance was statistically significant, $\chi^2=345.1158$, $p<0.05$. As can be seen, students during the online courses' modality generated the highest performance (grades A & B). However, this discrepancy was primarily due to the large number of online courses in the survey. Looking at grades in relation to the mode of teaching, the difference in percentages between learners is small (Tanyel & Griffin, 2014). Within face-to-face learners

* Before running ANOVA, we tested the normality of the variable 'success rates' by comparing its mean, median, and mode. All three averages were found very close to each other and thus hypothesis of normality was accepted.

got 468 A grades (47.46% of total A grades earned) while online learners got 518 A grades (52.53% of total A grade's earned). Although, when reviewing the A grade regarding to total learners in each patch, it can be found that 518 of the 1068 online learners (48.50%) got as compared to 468 of 1430 (32.27%) face-to-face learners. Again, online learners scored relatively higher in this grade's classification. The latter measurements (grade sum as a percentage of sum of the respective teaching mode) better reflect their respective achievement levels. Given a chi-square value of 345.1158 with $p < 0.05$, had to reject our null hypothesis. There is a statistically significant difference found in the teaching modes in terms of performance scores.

Table 3 Contingency table for student's academic performance in modules

Comparison	A	B	C	D	F
2019-2020 (face-to-face)	171	230	206	107	35
<i>Expected count</i>	296	265	134	45	11
2020-2021 (Online)	518	373	147	29	0
<i>Expected count</i>	421	377	190	63	16
2021-2022 (Hybrid)	297	279	92	12	1
<i>Expected count</i>	269	240	121	40	10

Discussion

The study showed that there was an upward trend in the success rates of the students in the CAMSJ during the pandemic of COVID-19 by the time, and by the mode of teaching (Table 1). There was a significant improvement in the success rate during the online mode of teaching during 2020-21, compared to 2019-20 when the mode of teaching was completely face-to-face. The same trend continued in 2021-22 even though the mode of teaching was blended learning, where most of the instructional teaching was face-to-face and some mode of teaching instruction was online. Our results are consistent with the work of (Supriya et al., 2021), which also showed that transition to online teaching-learning had a positive impact on the overall success rate of the students, which could be due to increased flexibility of the instructors, giving leniency in the submission of the assignments, availability of the recorded lectures which help students to learn at their own pace and manage their time in a better way. Another reason could be that instructors were more flexible in assessments, as during 2020-21 most of the assessment was online (Villanueva et al., 2020). But the following trend of increased success rate in 2021-22, when the hybrid mode of teaching was used and the assessment was completely face-to-face, could be explained that students were accustomed to technology and independence which promoted their critical thinking and decision-making skills. Some of the earlier studies have also suggested that technology-assisted courses have a strong positive impact on students' performance (Özgen et al, 2021). As a result, different universities around the world are stepping up efforts to design more flexible courses, technology-enhanced teaching, and self-study modules that reduce student learning stress. Prime qualitative interactions of the instructors with the students have positive impacts on student learning which continued even during the reversal of face-to-face teaching in the current academic year 2021-22, showing a maintained trend of increase in the success rate of the students. The curriculum structure of online courses during the pandemic was not intended for online learning. The curriculum was designed for normal, offline learning and it had to be tailored to suit the needs of online learning, which may have augmented the student learning outcome, where the instructor in an online environment performed two major roles: a designer and a facilitator (Martin et al., 2019). The instructor who offered the online class during the pandemic had additional responsibilities and acted like a "facilitator" to facilitate learning and actively participate in discussions with the learner (Douglas et al., 2020) to enhance learning success and student satisfaction. Students needed to adapt to the changing environment, improve their technical skills during the process and provide technical expertise to students unfamiliar with this environment. The results showed that facilitation and teacher knowledge are important determinants of learning success and student satisfaction during online learning in a pandemic (Hansen, 2020).

The results of the ANOVA showed there is a significant difference in success rates in face-to-face, online, and hybrid modes of teaching. This result indicates that teaching methodology matters a lot in addition to the other factors. For the online teaching mode, the success rate was higher. The likely contributing factors in improving the success rate are saving commuting time, more flexibility in reaching out to online resource material, teaching quality of online courses, assessments method flexibility, and the intervention of innovative technologies that increase the curiosity in the students and help them learning in interesting ways. Our results are in line with Armstrong-Mensah (2020), A. Selvaraj (2021), and Saadeh et al. (2021).

According to the analysis shown in Figure 2 and Table 3, students generated the highest performance (grades A and B) during the online and hybrid course modes. In the previous study (Armstrong-Mensah et al., 2020)

students agreed that the faculty did not need to be physically present and found that the faculty communicated their expectations for the course and were available to provide the course materials and ratings. Less commuting, more time spent on chores and with family, and more time management were a part of the positive result of increased performance during the online mode.

Students reported that switching to distance learning significantly increased their learning volume, but this did not have an impact on their motivation to learn and completed the task on time (Armstrong-Mencer et al., 2020). It shows that despite the challenges, the students were able to excel the semester with satisfactory grades. In the light of encouraging findings about distance learning, it suggests that the best way to move forward is to adjust expectations and lower ratings that overestimate online engagement and content acquisition. It also requires that the teacher check in to the students from time to time and discuss academic challenges with them in order to strike the right balance without overwhelming them. As teachers become more effective in using technology and institutions evolve their technology infrastructure, the quality of interaction in online courses improves. Appropriate communication channels need to be set up between students and teachers so that students can answer their questions and interact more in an online learning environment. Students need to take advantage of the abundant resources available on the internet.

According to the APA Work Group of the Board of Educational Affairs (1997), the learner-targeted standards endorse that scholars have to be inclined to make investments in the time required to finish character route assignments. Online teachers have to be obsessed with growing authentic academic assets that actively join beginners and inspire them closer to proficient performances. For higher overall performance, each teacher and college students have the same responsibility. When the learner faces any hassle to apprehend the concepts, he desires to make inquiries for the teacher's solutions (Gopal et al., 2021). Thus, we are able to conclude that "teacher quality, student's expectation, set off feedback, and effective route design" significantly affect college students' online acquisition of knowledge process.

Conclusion

Our results make us optimistic about our students' future learning results and performance. Therefore, online teaching experience seems important, during pandemic students and teachers have accumulated rewarding experiences. Online learning courses have dramatically improved student performance, and this overall call for growth in online learning can be cost-effective and efficient, time and location diversity, and the ability to participate digitally in sessions. It has been shown to be enhanced for some reason; Space to perform various tasks, less distracting compared to face-to-face classes. With proper initiative, online learning can dominate the discipline (Selvaraj, 2021), particularly, for medical education applying a hybrid model in teaching in which traditional laboratory dissection is combined with remote learning (Shahrivini et al., 2021) is highly recommended. Future research needs to be conducted to better understand the impact of technology adoption on student satisfaction and perceived learning. Future research needs to focus on factors that influence students' opinion of accepting online learning after the pandemic.

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